

Signals, Action-Reaction and Special Relativity in a Newtonian Framework Part 2

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Newtonian mechanics is well-known for introducing the concept of conservation of energy and momentum, but it treats interactions as occurring at $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$. The problem with this limitation is that photons have energy E and momentum p and should uphold conservation of energy and momentum, but also have a wavelength and interfere with a two-slit apparatus. This leads to uncertainties in both Δx and Δt (see (1)) and yet momentum and energy must still be conserved. It seems that one cannot simply use Newtonian $F=dp/dt$ and F and $-F$ (action-reaction) or determinism to establish conservation laws for the photon.

Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, upholds conservation of momentum and energy yet introduces the free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass. Newtonian mechanics is then seen as the high energy, tiny wavelength, tiny frequency limit of quantum mechanics.

This begs the question: Where does special relativity sit? Historically, it was seen as an enhancement to Newtonian mechanics for v of the order of c (speed of light in a vacuum), but the complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ relative to each other (used to derive special relativity) does not force one to consider interactions occurring in $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$. An object is simply at rest or moving/translating with constant v in the case that a particle has a rest mass.

Special relativity accommodates a photon $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4 \rightarrow E=pc$ for $m_0=0$ and $E=pc$ is consistent with a wave equation. Thus, it seems that special relativity is actually consistent with quantum mechanics, but that the complementarity principle is a fundamental one so that $E=m_0c^2/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p=m_0v/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ for a free particle in both quantum and Newtonian cases. If special relativity is consistent with quantum mechanics, then the $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ structure should emerge from it and conservation of momentum and energy should also appear.

It is our goal to try to show that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may be used in special relativity to describe both a photon and particle with rest mass. Even though a photon moves like a self-wave ($E=pc$), with action-reaction (linked with electric and magnetic fields), we argue that it is the action-reaction feature which should be common to both a photon and particle with rest mass and that this should be linked to conservation of momentum and energy because it is linked with force. We suggest that for a particle with rest mass, even though all points seem to translate in space with v , that there are action-reaction remnants which do not disappear when the particle is first accelerated. We argue that m_0, E, p are the only interaction information one has and that one must describe this action-reaction in such a way that it yields conservation of energy and momentum. The actual motion/speed of both the photon and particle with rest mass is secondary.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics is well-known for predicting conservation of energy and momentum, two key ideas of interactions. The point, however, is that it treats an interaction as occurring at:

$$dx \rightarrow 0 \text{ and } dt \rightarrow 0 \quad ((1))$$

((1)) holds because one may follow a particle as $x(t)$ for all x, t . Even if an interaction were to take place in a region Δx and time interval Δt , one may subdivide this into smaller $dx \rightarrow 0, dt \rightarrow 0$ regions and follow the exact interaction yielding $x(t)$. In other words, everything is deterministic and there is no probability if one follows the details closely enough.

A problem which arises with this viewpoint is light (i.e. a photon). A photon has energy and momentum, as does a Newtonian particle, and these must be conserved. The photon, however, has a wavelength and interferes with a 2-slit apparatus, meaning that there is an uncertainty of Δx (and also Δt - see (1)). One cannot have determinism, i.e. ((1)), but it is:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((2))$$

which leads to the concept of conservation of momentum and ((2)) is deterministic. An interfering photon must conserve energy and momentum, but the treatment is probabilistic and one cannot possibly follow the interaction as $x(t)$ and impose conservation of momentum at each x and t . As a result, Newtonian mechanics applies to a particle with rest mass and has some difficulties explaining a photon (as long as there is no mechanical medium creating the photon, i.e. the photon is a self-wave).

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics upholds conservation of energy and momentum, but assumes that a free particle or photon must be described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In other words, there is a complex probability involved with interactions allowing for 2-slit interference and uncertainty of Δx and Δt . One must have conservation of momentum and energy at the same time that probabilistic interactions are occurring. This seems to imply that the description of the probabilistic interactions must uphold conservation of energy and momentum, especially in the case of interference.

This seems to be the case, as is well-known as:

$$\int \exp(-i p_{\text{final}} x) \exp(i p_{\text{initial}} x) dx = 0 \text{ unless } p_{\text{final}} = p_{\text{initial}} \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{and } \int \exp(i E_{\text{final}} t) \exp(-i E_{\text{initial}} t) dt = 0 \text{ unless } E_{\text{final}} = E_{\text{initial}} \quad ((3b))$$

Conservation of energy and momentum need not be a property which follows from enforcing $dx \rightarrow 0, dt \rightarrow 0$. If \hbar/E and \hbar/p are tiny, then Δt and Δx become so small that they are essentially 0 and one retrieves approximately the Newtonian case. Thus, one speaks of quantum mechanics becoming classical mechanics (Newtonian) in the high energy limit. The

question that now remains is: What does special relativity imply? (There is also the question: How does quantum mechanics emerge, which has so far been ignored.)

Special Relativity

Special relativity seems to be based on the notion of complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ with respect to each other. This seems to be a fundamental idea, like conservation of energy and momentum. One may derive, from this idea alone and the notion of m_0 transforming into a flux proportional to $m_0 v$ and a new inertia E :

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}, \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((4))$$

From this one idea of complementarity, without any notion of an interaction taking place at x with $dx \rightarrow 0$ and t with $dt \rightarrow 0$, one has a certain amount of information, based on E, p, m_0 , describing interaction variables. Even though the results ((4)) become Newtonian in the $v \ll c$ limit, there is no explicit constraint of an interaction occurring at a point. Furthermore, for $m_0 = 0$, one obtains:

$$E = pc \quad ((5))$$

which applies to a photon.

Why would one consider an $m_0 = 0$ solution at all? The complementarity of frames moving at a constant $-v$ to each other has been applied to a particle with rest mass m_0 (not one with $m_0 = 0$) and is very much a translational motion idea. Not only is the center-of-mass moving with v , but all other points on the object with rest mass. We suggest that inclusion of $m_0 = 0$ (i.e. a photon solution) seems to be completely contradictory to the notion of translation of points (unless one applies it to the origin of a co-ordinate axes system). In the next section, we try to determine the physical consequences of including a photon solution in the complementarity of frames idea.

Special Relativity and the Photon

The photon seems to be an object with its own special properties as seen from interference-diffraction and Maxwell's equations. It thus seems surprising that it should appear in a solution resulting from complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ relative to each other. The photon has the same speed as seen from either frame and so the whole idea of momentum as a kind of flux linked with $m_0 v$ does not apply. Furthermore, one does not think of a photon as an object with a shape and many points which translate, at least if one considers the wave solutions for the electric and magnetic fields from Maxwell's equations. We thus ask: What does $E = pc$ ((5)) really mean?

A particle with rest mass follows $x = vt$ and a photon, $x = ct$. In both cases, there is energy E and momentum p . For a photon, like for a particle with rest mass, p is proportional to the physical impact with a target and E (for the photon) is linked to a rise in temperature. These seem to be experimentally verifiable and directly linked to interactions. Speed, however, is linked with motion in space, Δx and Δt and the form of $E = pc$ or $1/p = c/E$ suggest that $1/p$ and $1/E$ act like intervals in space and time even though E and p are interaction

variables. At first one may argue that this is merely a coincidence, but we argue that given that E and p are interaction variables and that c is the same in all frames, there should not be so direct a relation as $E=pc$ unless these interaction variables are really linked to motion in space-time. Given that they are interaction variables, this motion does not seem to be a simple translation and this is a main point we wish to make.

Interaction variables like E and p should be linked with force and action-reaction, if in fact they are linked at all with motion. This is the opposite of motion as simple translation which seems to be implied by the complementarity of frames picture. The extreme solution of $m_0=0$, leads to an extreme view of motion as linked with E and p because it is linked with forces and action-reaction. (The periodic solutions for the electric and magnetic fields from Maxwell's equations show that this is indeed the case.) If E and p are linked with forces and action-reaction in a periodic manner suggested by:

$$c = E / p \text{ compared with wave velocity} = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad ((6))$$

then this self-wave, involving action-reaction and a mechanism for interaction through the electric and magnetic fields, should be linked with conservation of momentum and energy directly.

As a result, one has the complementarity of frames notion allowing for a photon solution which describes motions strictly in terms of action-reaction and this should be tied to the physical notion of conservation (of energy and momentum).

To see this explicitly, one may consider the solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and note that:

$$\text{Conservation of momentum: } \int dx \exp(-i p_{\text{final}} x) \exp(ip_{\text{initial}} x) = 0 \text{ if } p_{\text{final}} \neq p_{\text{initial}} \quad ((7a))$$

$$\text{Conservation of momentum: } \int dt \exp(i E_{\text{final}} t) \exp(-i E_{\text{initial}} t) = 0 \text{ if } E_{\text{final}} \neq E_{\text{initial}} \quad ((7b))$$

We argue that it makes sense for the mechanism describing the periodicity of the photon using E and p to be linked with conservation of energy and momentum because the usual $dp/dt = F$ and action reaction (i.e. F and $-F$) associated with following a particle in x,t does not apply to a photon, especially if it diffracts or interferes with a slit system. The approach used to describe the action-reaction type motion linked with interaction must enforce conservation of energy and momentum.

One may argue that these ideas may apply to a photon, but it is completely different for a particle with rest mass.

Particle with Rest Mass

A particle with rest mass must also have conservation of energy and momentum, but the complementarity of frames moving at constant $-v$ with respect to each other does apply to such a system. In fact, it portrays motion as a translation of different points of the object (each moving with the same velocity). Although all the various dm (little mass pieces) must move with the

same speed, we argue that the physical consequences of applying a force to accelerate a rest mass to v seem to be lost in this view. The complementarity principle represents a complicated system of molecules and fields by a simple parameter m_0 and then finds a relation between m_0 , E and p . This relation is fine, but we argue that action-reaction effects are created when one accelerates a particle.

In general, a force may be imposed at one end and signals need to travel through the mass together with resulting action-reaction behaviour. We suggest that even though the particle with rest mass ultimately moves with v , these action-reaction features do not disappear (like in the photon case which is all action-reaction). The question then becomes: How does one describe the action-reaction features?

The complementarity notion leads one to describe the entire system in terms of the information: m_0 , v , E and p . If one does not wish to introduce other variables, can one describe the action-reaction which is present due to the force?

First, we suggest that any remaining action-reaction effects are linked with not only internal force, but the possibility of the particle interacting with an outside source, just like with the photon. Secondly, one would expect the description to enforce conservation of momentum and energy as it is force based. Thus, even though a particle with rest mass does not follow $E=pc$ and one cannot make a wave argument based on this, one can make an $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ argument based on conservation of energy and momentum. Given that one is describing the system by the information E and p and that these are linked to interaction, then $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is an expression which allows for conservation of energy and momentum and shows that even though the center-of-mass may seem to move in a deterministic way ($x=vt$), the action-reaction remnant effects from the original acceleration do not lead to localization in space and time (otherwise one would have no action-reaction in the first place). Thus, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may be used for both a photon and particle with rest mass based on action-reaction arguments (although only the photon uses these to create its speed) and conservation of momentum and energy.

As a result, we argue that it is not an accident that quantum mechanics and special relativity both describe a photon and particle with rest mass. We suggest that this means that they both must lead to the notion of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ with Newtonian mechanics appearing not only for $v \ll c$, but also for wavelength and frequency becoming tiny (almost 0) in the Newtonian scale. After all, one still has nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, so $v \ll c$ is not sufficient for arguing that Newtonian mechanics applies. In fact, free particle quantum mechanics (ignoring spin) seems to arise from the principles of complementarity of frames moving at $-v$ with respect to each other and conservation of momentum and energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics deals with interactions associated with $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ and so does not describe the interference/diffraction of a photon even though it has an E and p . Both special relativity and quantum mechanics, however, describe a photon ($m_0=0$) and particle with rest mass. Special relativity is based on a complementarity of frames moving at constant $-v$ with respect to each other and one may consider a particle with constant speed. In such a sense, one does not have to worry about the specifics of how a force

accelerated the particle etc. One seems to have a translational viewpoint. The problem is that given $EE = ppcc + momocccc$, one may set $m_0=0$ and obtain a photon solution. At first one may argue that a photon has E and p and so $E=pc$ is simply a relationship. We argue that given the specific form: $1/p = c 1/E$, the interaction variables (the only interaction information available) are linked to space-time motion, which is unusual. We suggest that this means that they must be linked with action-reaction (i.e. internal force) which may also interact with external bodies. Thus, if conservation of energy and momentum are to appear for a photon, they should be linked with this internal action-reaction force. We suggest that the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ allows for this. One cannot rely on Newtonian mechanics for conservation of momentum and energy for a photon because the photon is not deterministic when diffracting/interfering.

We then note that special relativity describes both a photon and particle with rest mass, just like free particle quantum mechanics. The photon solution has already been discussed and leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ because E and p are the only interaction variables present and the motion itself is based on action-reaction. A particle with rest mass, however, seems to translate in space. It does not follow $E=pc$ or even $E=pv$. We argue, however, that physically the effects of action-reaction, which are stirred up when the particle is first accelerated, do not disappear. We note that $EE = ppcc + momocccc$ is a relation between interaction variables and does not contradict the idea of action-reaction effects remaining.

A particle with rest mass is a complicated object with molecules and fields which are being summarized by the variables m_0 , E and p . This suggests there should be a way to describe the action-reaction effects within the particle (which should also be available to interact with outside objects) using E and p and that this description should also lead to conservation of energy and momentum. We suggest that one may again use $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ even though this does not create spatial motion. It describes action-reaction and conservation of momentum and energy as argued in Part 1.

References

1. Ruggeri, Frances R. Two-Slit Interference Separating Particles in Time as Well as Space? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)